

Impact of Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction of Nepalese Commercial Banks: With Special Reference to Biratnagar Metropolitan City

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Abstract

The aim of this paper is to study the impact of service quality, by using SERVQUAL model on customer satisfaction in Nepalese commercial banks with special reference to Biratnagar metropolitan city. In order to achieve the aim, survey of bank customers has been performed with structured questionnaire. The 300 sample were randomly selected from the branches of 15 commercial banks located in Biratnagar. Correlation and multiple regressions were used to investigate the relationship between dependent and independent variables. The correlation results indicate that there is a positive correlation between the dimensions of service quality and customer satisfaction. The result of the regression shows that customer satisfaction is influenced by responsiveness, tangibles, empathy, and assurance significantly while reliability found to be insignificant.

Keywords: Service quality, SERVQUAL, Customer satisfaction, Nepalese Commercial banks.

Introduction

In the present scenario banking sector has gone through dramatic growth and change. The economic liberalization, intensified competition, advance technology has fueled this change (Khatri, 2014). Due to this it raises intensive competition among banks and led banking sector to develop different strategies to attract and retain customer. It is pivotal for all banking industry to understand the needs of the customer and deliver the services based on their needs which in turn will pave way for achieving customer satisfaction. (Parasuraman, Zeithaml, & Berry, 1985) and urge that the key strategy for the success and survival of any business is the deliverance of quality services to customers. The level of service quality can be use as a differentiator by bank in order to respond competition and to satisfy the customer. If customers are offered services as they expected or exceed the expectation than they will have positive attitude towards the firm. Any lack in services or in quality may lead to dissatisfaction among the customer and result to lost customer. Good customer service is essential to successful organization and customer retention. It enhances reputation, improves customer retention, attracts new

customers and increases financial performance and profitability (Julian & Ramaseshan, 1994 ; Zeithaml, 1996). Delivering quality service helps to respond competition which in turn helps in satisfying the customer as a result it helps in retaining customer (Anand & Selvaraj, 2013).

Service quality is an important construct (Nochai & Nochai, 2013) and antecedent to customer satisfaction (Bhatta & Durgapal, 2016). The perception of service quality results from a comparison of consumer expectations with actual service performance (Parasuraman et al. 1985). In simple words, it is a comparison of expectations with performance. According to Lewis and Booms (1983) service quality is a measure of how well the delivery of service level do match with customer expectations. Delivering quality service means conforming to customer expectations on a continuous basis. Customer expectations are beliefs of customer regarding service which serve as standard against which service performance is judged.

Jamal Service quality and customer satisfaction are important concepts in marketing. The key to sustainable competitive advantage depend on high quality service which in turn results in satisfied customers (Shemwell, Yavas, & Bilgin, 1998). An empirical test of the reciprocity between satisfaction and quality across several service industries found that service quality can be seen as a determinant of satisfaction as a result influences purchase intentions (Cronin & Taylor, 1992). According to Oliver (1980), satisfaction is a result of service quality encounter and comparing that encounter with what was expected.

This paper aims to identify the relationship between dimensions of service quality and customer satisfaction. Further the main purpose of this study to examine the service quality and its impact on satisfaction of customers of commercial banks in Biratnagar metropolitan city, by using SERVQUAL tool (Parasuraman, Zeithaml, & Berry, 1988).

Statement of the problem

Banks today are facing lots of pressure due to intense competition and are adopting various strategies to attract, retain and satisfy the customer. Maintaining good service has become a prerequisite for the banks to satisfy and retain the customer. . Reviewing number of studies found service quality as an important tool to measure customer satisfaction. Otoo(2016) conducted a study which examined the effect of customer service quality on customer satisfaction in commercial banks in Ghana. The result shows that service reliability, assurance, empathy and tangibles are significant determinants of customer's satisfaction with their service quality. The all five dimensions of service quality: tangibility, reliability, responsiveness and assurance have significant effects on customer satisfaction (Huang, Bruce, & Ching, 2017).

Ahmad & Kyriaki (2009) found reliability, tangibility and empathy of service quality positively related with customer satisfaction. Study reveals that a satisfied customer is six times more likely to repurchase a product and share his experience with five or six other people (Grönroos, 2000) and unsatisfied customer can banish more business than ten highly satisfied customer (Mohsan, Nawaz, Khan, Shaukat, & Aslam, 2011).

The research undertaken by Shanka (2012) found that there is a positive correlation between the service quality and customer satisfaction. The results of the regression test showed that service quality have positive impact on customer satisfaction. The result showed that empathy, responsiveness and tangibility plays important role in satisfying the customer. The research further states that increase in customer satisfaction leads to high level of customer commitment and loyalty.

The quality of service and impact on customer satisfaction in banking sector of Nepal is one of the topic that carry high importance in the field of management studies and to those institutions that value quality service. There are only few studies done in the field of service quality in context of Nepal. Where as, maximum number of research done in the field of service quality and customer

satisfaction in the developed countries. Identifying and measuring service quality and level of satisfaction of bank customers becomes inevitable in the present scenario. Therefore, a study relating to service quality dimensions and its impact on customer satisfaction in Nepalese context is considered necessary. Hence, the research has been undertaken to identify and examine the impact of service quality on customer satisfaction in Nepalese commercial bank by using SERVQUAL model.

The following research issues were addressed regarding service quality:

- What is the association between service quality dimensions and customer satisfaction in commercial banks of Biratnagar Metropolitan city?
- To what extent dimensions of service quality influences the customer satisfaction in commercial banks of Biratnagar Metropolitan city?

Objectives of the Study

The purpose of this study is to assess the impact of service quality on customer satisfaction in commercial banks. Hence, the objective of the study has been classified into general objective and specific objective.

General objective

- To examine the relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction in Nepalese commercial banks with special reference to Biratnagar metropolitan city.
- To measure the degree of relationship of service quality dimensions on customer satisfaction in Nepalese commercial banks in Biratnagar.

Specific objectives

- To determine the perception of customers about the various service quality provided by Nepalese commercial banks in Biratnagar.
- To find the association between the sub dimension of service quality and customer satisfaction in Nepalese commercial banks in Biratnagar.
- To measure the degree of relationship of service quality dimensions on customer satisfaction in Nepalese commercial banks in Biratnagar.
- To identify the most important dimension of service quality on customer satisfaction in Nepalese commercial banks in Biratnagar.

Literature Review

Service quality as compared to product quality is difficult to define and measure due to its unique features like intangibility, heterogeneity and inseparability. Despite of this, several researchers have tried to define service quality in different ways. Service quality has been defined as the comparison of consumer expectations with actual service performance (Gronroos, 1984; Parasuraman et al., 1988). It is the customer who compares the quality of service based on their expectation and perception of the actual service.

Grönroos (1984) defined service quality based on two dimensions: technical dimension and functional dimension. Technical refers to what service provider delivers during the service provision whereas; functional dimension refers to how the service employee provides the service. According to Gronroos's model (1984) consumer's view regarding technical and functional services form the perceived quality. In the same paper researcher claimed that in order to manage perceived service quality a firm has to match expected service and the perceived service.

Parasuraman et al. (1985) proposes the 10 dimensions of service quality and constituted a GAP model. At first model had 22 pairs of likert type items, where at one part it measures perceived level of service quality by respondent and the other part measures expected level of service quality by respondent. Later Parasuraman et al. (1988) developed multi item scale for measuring service quality called SERVQUAL tool with 5 dimensions- Tangibles, Reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy.

Cronin & Taylor (1992) developed SERVPERF model which is a performane-only model for measuring service quality. Kang &James (2004) extended Gronroos model by adding process related dimension based on how the quality of the service delivery received by the customer.In the same way there are other models regarding service quality. Rust & Oliver (1994) proposed a three dimensional non tested model which include service product, service delivery, and service environment. Frost & Kumar (2000) developed an internal service quality model called INTERSERVQUAL based on the GAP model (Parasuraman et al. 1985) and the SERVQUAL (Parasuraman et al. 1988). INERSERVQUAL model measures the service quality on internal customers.

According to Jamal & Anastasiadou(2009), reliability, tangibility and empathy positively related with customer satisfaction. The study conducted by Sulieman (2011) found that reliability, tangibility, responsiveness and assurance have significant and positive relationship with customer satisfaction. Bhatta & Durgapal (2016) undertook a study in Service quality by using SERVPERF approach found that there is a strong correlation between service quality dimensions and customer satisfaction. The study revealed reliability, tangibility, empathy and responsiveness as statistically significant predictors of customer satisfaction. Furthermore, Neupane & Devkota (2017) undertaken a study of private hospitals to examine the impacts of service quality dimensions on patient satisfaction in Nepal reveal that service quality is positively correlated with customer/ patient satisfaction. The result shows that service quality and patient satisfaction (customer) are positively correlated.

A review on dimensions of service quality models conducted by Yarimoglu(2014) stated that SERVQUAL was the most used model in measuring service quality. Although the model was criticised by many but the study stated that SERVQUAL has become the most widely applied scale in researches. SERVQUAL model helps researchers to examine different service industries such as: health care, banking, financial and education (Nycek, Morales, Ladhari, & Pons, 2002).

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1 Theoretical Framework

Source: Based on SERVQUAL model (Parasuraman et al., 1988)

The variables of the study are five dimensions of service quality and customer satisfaction. The five dimensions: tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy are based on SERVQUAL tool (Parasuraman et al., 1988). Tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy are independent variable to the dependent variable customer satisfaction. These five dimensions are defined as follow:

Tangibles: The physical surroundings represented by objects and subjects.

Reliability: The service provider's ability to provide accurate and dependable services.

Responsiveness: It is a firm's willingness to assist its customers by providing fast and efficient service performances.

Assurance: It is a diverse feature that provides confidence to customers.

Empathy: the service firm's readiness to provide each customer with personal approach.

Regression Model

Customer Satisfaction = f (Tangibility, Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance, Empathy)

$$CS = b_0 + b_1 Tan + b_2 Rel + b_3 Res + b_4 Assu + b_5 Emp + e$$

$$(b_1, b_2, b_3, b_4, b_5 > 0)$$

Where, b_1, b_2, b_3, b_4, b_5 are coefficients;

b_0 = constant; e = error term;

Tan = Tangibles; Rel = Reliability; Res = Responsiveness; Assu = Assurance; Emp = Empathy.

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses are formulated for this study.

H1: There is a significant relationship between tangibility in the service quality and customer satisfaction.

H2: There is a significant relationship between reliability in the service quality and customer satisfaction.

H3: There is a significant relationship between responsiveness in the service quality and customer satisfaction.

H4: There is a significant relationship between assurance in the service quality and customer satisfaction.

H5: There is a significant relationship between empathy in the service quality and customer satisfaction.

H6: There is a significant impact of tangibility in the service quality and customer satisfaction.

H7: There is a significant impact of reliability in the service quality and customer satisfaction.

H8: There is a significant impact of responsiveness in the service quality and customer satisfaction.

H9: There is a significant impact of assurance in the service quality and customer satisfaction.

H10: There is a significant impact of empathy in the service quality and customer satisfaction.

Research Methodology

The methodological aspect related to the study gives an overview of population, sample, data collection method and analysis procedure. This research is a quantitative research design to identify and analyze the impact of service quality on customer satisfaction. In which service quality is viewed as independent variable and customer satisfaction is considered as dependent variable.

Population and Sample

The population of this study consists of all the customers of 27 commercial banks that are operating in Nepal. The study is conducted in Biratnagar Metropolitan city of Nepal. 300 Customers of 15 commercial banks were taken as sample of the study. Questionnaires were distributed using survey method and respondents were identified through random sampling method.

Data Collection and Analysis

In this study primary data were collected through administering the structured questionnaires. The literature study shows that the SERVQUAL scale by Parasuraman et al. (1988) has been proven to be one of the best ways to measure the quality of service rendered to customers. Hence, the questionnaires were based on the five dimensions of SERVQUAL scale (tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy. All the statements based on these five dimensions were measured on a five point Likert scale, ranging from strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (5). The questionnaire consists of two parts. Part A considers the respondent's personal profile and part B consist of statements relating to service quality and customer satisfaction. The data collected through structured questionnaire were statistically analyzed. Correlation coefficient and multiple regression analysis were used to analyze the significant relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction. The data analysis for this study conducted through statistical package for social science (SPSS) version 20.

Reliability Statistics

The internal consistency of the research instrument was tested by Cronbach's alpha. The values of alpha (α) were derived by running Cronbach's alpha if item deleted and shows that removing any item from the list of questions has increased the Cronbach's alpha value. The values of alpha were found to be more than 0.5 (Appendix-1). It implies that there exists internal consistency in the responses to the questionnaire. (Jamal & Anastasiadou, 2009)

Test of Multicollinearity

In order to run multiple regression analysis in SPSS, enter method was used and to determine the multi-collinearity among independent variables, tolerance test and variance inflation factor (VIF) were used. The test of collinearity shows that tolerance value of all the independent variables are less than 1 and VIF values are also below 5 (Appendix-2). This indicates that there is no multi-collinearity (Yoo, Mayberry, Bae, Singh, Peter, & Lillard Jr, 2014).

Results and Analysis

Respondent's Demographic Characteristics

The analysis of the data gathered revealed that male represents 67.3% of 300 respondents, while the ratio of female is 32.7%. The results indicate that most of the respondents are from 18-30 and 31-50 years old. Smaller groups of respondents are aged 51 (8%). With regard to educational level, respondents with SLC and intermediate are the largest group of respondents comprising 42% of the respondents while bachelor degree holders represent 38% which is the second largest group. Finally school level and master and above level comprises only 11.3% and 8.7% respectively. With regard to frequency of use, majority of the respondents are not frequent users; they use the service at most once in a month (Appendix-3).

Descriptive Statistics, Correlation and Multiple Regressions

The mean score for the five dimensions of service quality shows that highest mean is scored by assurance followed by reliability and responsiveness. The least mean score is for empathy followed

by tangibles. The mean score of assurance dimension of service quality is 17.24. While mean score of reliability and responsiveness are 12.7 and 11.95 respectively. The least mean score of empathy is 8.24 and tangible is 7.25 (Appendix-4).

In correlation analysis (Appendix-5) independent variable found to be positively and significantly correlated with customer satisfaction at p-value 0.001. The highest correlation is between responsiveness and customer satisfaction (0.581) followed by tangibles (0.542) and assurance (0.492) while a comparatively weak correlation is found between reliability and customer satisfaction. The independent variables of the study were able to explain around 48% of the total variation of customer satisfaction (Annex 6). The ANNOVA table (Appendix 6) showed that the model with these five predictors statistically significantly predict the dependent variable ($F(5, 294) = 55.29$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.001$) and hence shows the goodness of the fit model. Further, result of regression analysis indicates that customer satisfaction is influenced by tangibles, responsiveness, assurance and empathy significantly while reliability is not significant to customer satisfaction.

Hypothesis Testing

Table 1 Results of Hypotheses Testing

Hypotheses	Values scored	Result	Tools
H1: There is a significant relationship between tangibility and customer satisfactions.	$r = 0.542$ $p = 0.000$ ($p < 0.001$)	Accepted	Correlation
H2: There is a significant relationship between reliability and customer satisfaction.	$r = 0.436$ $p = 0.000$ ($p < 0.001$)	Accepted	Correlation
H3: There is a significant relationship between responsiveness and customer satisfaction.	$r = 0.581$ $p = 0.000$ ($p < 0.001$)	Accepted	Correlation
H4: There is a significant relationship between assurance and customer satisfaction.	$r = 0.492$ $p = 0.000$ ($p < 0.001$)	Accepted	Correlation
H5: There is a significant relationship between empathy and customer satisfaction.	$r = 0.525$ $p = 0.000$ ($p < 0.001$)	Accepted	Correlation
H6: There is a significant impact of tangibility on customer satisfaction.	$\beta = 0.228$ $p = 0.000$ ($p < 0.05$)	Accepted	Multiple regression
H7: There is a significant impact of reliability on customer satisfaction	$\beta = 0.065$ $p = 0.211$ ($p < 0.05$)	Failed to accept (not significant)	Multiple regression
H8: There is a significant impact of responsiveness on customer satisfaction	$\beta = 0.251$ $p = 0.000$ ($p < 0.05$)	Accepted	Multiple regression
H9: There is a significant impact of assurance on customer satisfaction	$\beta = 0.172$ $p = 0.001$ ($p < 0.05$)	Accepted	Multiple regression
H10: There is a significant impact of empathy on customer satisfaction	$\beta = 0.194$ $p = 0.000$ ($p < 0.05$)	Accepted	Multiple regression

Discussions and Conclusions

To assess the service quality of commercial banks operating in Biratnagar metropolitan city of Nepal, the five dimensions (tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy) of service quality were used. The study revealed that Nepalese commercial banks are good in assurance, reliability and responsiveness. While the mean score values are lowest for tangibles and empathy. This means customers are not very satisfied regarding bank's physical facilities, tools, machines used and personal attention given by banks. This indicates inferior performance of these banks in those dimensions of service quality. Bank need to improve in those areas. Further the study shows that all the five dimensions of service quality are positively correlated with customer satisfaction. This indicates that service quality of bank is important for customer satisfaction and the result of the study is consistent with the results of previous studies in terms of direction of the relationship. Out of five dimensions, the study shows that responsiveness, tangibles and empathy are the dominant dimensions of customer satisfaction. Banking sectors need special attention regarding responsiveness, tangibility and empathy to customer as it has a significant positive relationship with customer satisfaction. Further the mean score of banks are lowest in tangibles and empathy as explained above hence banks are required to work more on tangibility and initializing the provision of individual customer caring, attention to the customer need. The result of regression analysis shows that dimensions of service quality contribute significantly to customer satisfaction at 5% significance levels. The analysis shows that 48% of the variance in customer satisfaction can be predicted by the service quality offered by commercial banks. Customer satisfaction is influenced by responsiveness, tangibles, empathy, and assurance significantly. While reliability found to be insignificant in customer satisfaction. This research provides some insight into service quality in banks of Nepalese commercial banks by using SERVQUAL tools. However, there is still a chance to extend the study by using SERVPERF tools and conducting a comparative analysis on SERVPERF and SERVQUAL scores. Further, by incorporating other dimensions of service quality the study may be conducted in other service industries.

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Appendices
Appendix 1 Reliability Test

Service quality dimensions	Items selected	Cronbach Alpha (α)
Tangibles	Item 1 and 2	0.86
Reliability	Item 5, 6 and 8	0.73
Responsiveness	Item 9,10 and 11	0.6
Assurance	Item 13,14,15 and 16	0.71
Empathy	Item 17,19and 20	0.82
Customer satisfaction	Item 22,23,24 and 25	0.78

Appendix 2 Test of Collinearity

Independent Variables	Collinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance	VIF
Tangibles	.651	1.536
Reliability	.650	1.539
Responsiveness	.543	1.841
Assurance	.690	1.449
Empathy	.638	1.567

Appendix 3 Demographic Profile of the Customers

Gender	Frequency	Valid Percent
Female	98	32.7
Male	202	67.3
Age		
18-30	135	45.0
31-50	144	48.0
51 and above	21	7.0
Educational Level		
School	34	11.3
SLC and intermediate	126	42.0
Bachelor	114	38.0
Master and Above	26	8.7
Frequency of using bank		
Daily	42	14.0
Weekly	76	25.3
Monthly	143	47.7
Other	39	13.0
Profession		
Student	56	18.7
Employee	148	49.3
Businessman	67	22.3
House wife	29	9.7

Appendix 4 Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Customer Satisfaction	16.7667	2.31591	300
Tangibles	8.2467	1.72309	300
Reliability	12.7033	1.79799	300
Responsiveness	11.9500	1.84178	300
Assurance	17.2433	1.74574	300
Empathy	7.2533	1.66886	300

Appendix 5 Correlation Matrix (n=300)

	Customer Satisfaction (CS)	Tangibles	Reliability	Responsiveness	Assurance	Empathy
CS	1.000					
Tangibles	.542	1.000				
Reliability	.436	.337	1.000			
Responsiveness	.581	.532	.523	1.000		
Assurance	.492	.402	.423	.466	1.000	
Empathy	.525	.457	.461	.487	.431	1.000

Appendix 6 Regression Analysis

	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients		t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	3.504	1.023		3.424	.001
Tangibles	.306	.070	.228	4.393	.000
Reliability	.084	.067	.065	1.254	.211
Responsiveness	.316	.071	.251	4.425	.000
Assurance	.229	.067	.172	3.419	.001
Empathy	.269	.073	.194	3.702	.000
R= 0.696					
R2= 0.485					
Adjusted R2= 0.476					
F value = 55.295					
Sig. F=0.000					